

Signal Processing for Induction Motor Faults: Spectrogram Conversion of Current Waveforms

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ABSTRACT

3-phase induction motors are essential in both industrial and domestic settings, making their health and reliability vital for efficient operation and reduced maintenance costs. Over time, these motors are susceptible to faults in the stator and rotor due to continuous operation in harsh conditions. This paper explores the use of spectrogram analysis for fault detection in the bearings of 3-phase induction motors. The 3-phase stator current signals were initially acquired in a controlled laboratory setting, where an inner race fault was intentionally created in the bearing of the induction motor. These time-series signals were then transformed into 2D spectrogram images for further analysis. By transforming time-domain signals into time-frequency representations, spectrograms enable the identification and visualization of fault-specific frequencies. The methodology includes data collection, signal processing, and the development of tools to automate the conversion process.

KEYWORDS: *Induction motor, inner race bearing fault, image processing, spectrogram analysis.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Induction motors are a cornerstone of modern industrial systems, powering a wide range of applications, from manufacturing plants to household appliances. The reliability and performance of these motors are critical to maintaining operational efficiency and minimizing downtime, as any failure can lead to significant operational disruptions and increased maintenance costs. Over time, continuous operation under varying loads and harsh conditions leads to wear and tear, which may result in faults within the motor's components, particularly the stator (Vaniya et al., 2023), rotor (Vaniya et al., 2023), and bearings (Sheikh et al., 2022). Among these, bearing faults are one of the most common causes of motor failure (Mitra et al., 2023). As such, effective monitoring of motor health is crucial for early fault detection, allowing for timely interventions that prevent catastrophic failures and extend the motor's service life. Traditional fault detection methods such as electrical signal analysis (Sarkar et al., 2021), vibration analysis (Gundewar et al., 2021) and temperature monitoring (Khanjani et al., 2021), have been widely used; however, they often require specialized sensors and can be limited in their ability to detect certain types of faults. Among these, current signature analysis has gained popularity due to its non-invasive nature and ability to detect faults without the need for additional sensors (Liu et al., 2025). Various machine learning and deep learning models, such as ensemble learning (Kumar et al., 2021), artificial neural networks (ANN) (Pandarakone et al., 2019), and convolutional neural networks (CNN) (Lee et al., 2019), have demonstrated strong effectiveness in automating fault detection and improving diagnostic precision.

Extensive literature reviews highlight numerous contributions to bearing fault detection using vibration signals. However, research on stator current signal-based bearing fault detection remains limited. Given that induction motor current signal analysis can reveal anomalies associated with various fault types, this study aims to detect bearing faults by analysing three-phase stator currents. One effective method for converting time-domain current signals data into more insightful forms is spectrogram analysis (Halder et al., 2022). This paper investigates the use of spectrograms as a diagnostic tool for detecting bearing faults in induction motors, with a focus on transforming time-domain current

waveforms into 2D spectrogram images. This research centres on transforming and processing the current signal into a spectrogram to facilitate easier fault detection by identifying the specific fault frequencies. The main objectives include collecting data, converting 1-D current signals into spectrograms using Python, and establishing this conversion as a foundation for future fault detection efforts. Additionally, the study proposes the creation of a graphical user interface (GUI) to enhance user accessibility and simplify the process.

2. METHOD

2.1 Experimental Arrangements

The first step involves acquiring current signals from a 3-phase induction motor. The motor is monitored under controlled conditions with an intentionally induced inner race (IR) fault on the bearing of motor as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Photograph of bearing with crack in inner race

The following equipment and techniques are used to develop the experimental setup:

- **Motor and Generator Set:** A 3-phase induction motor, with specifications provided in Table 1, was utilized to capture 3-phase current signals under both healthy (H) and IR fault conditions. To simulate varying loads on the motor, a DC generator, also detailed in Table 1, was coupled with the motor. A set of lamps were connected to the DC generator to adjust the load conditions.

Table 1. Specifications of Induction Motor

Motor Rating		DC Generator Rating	
Parameters	Rating	Parameters	Rating
Phase	3	Phase	1
Power	2 HP	Power	2.2 kW
Voltage	415 V	Voltage	230V
Usage/Application	Industrial	Usage/Application	Industrial
Speed	1440 r.p.m.	Speed	1500 r.p.m.

- **Power Meter:** A YOKOGAWA make 3-phase power meter was used to collect the 3-phase current signals which will be used for further processing. The recorded data was stored in .CSV format on a PC, which was also interfaced to both the motor and the power meter.
- **Autotransformers:** 3 single phase auto-transformers were used to provide balanced 3-phase supply to the motor-generator set irrespective of inherent disturbances in the supply voltages.
- **Sampling Rate:** Signals were recorded at a high sampling rate (e.g., 20 kHz) to capture detailed frequency components present in the current waveforms.

The photograph and schematic diagram of the experimental setup for collecting the three-phase stator currents has been shown in Figure 2(a) and 2(b), respectively.

Figure 2. (a) Photograph and (b) schematic diagram of experimental arrangement

2.2 Background theory of Spectrogram

The spectrogram is a widely used time-frequency analysis technique that visualizes the frequency content of a signal as it varies over time. The core principle behind the spectrogram method is the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) (Misra et al., 2022). The STFT divides the signal into smaller, overlapping segments, each treated as approximately stationary over the duration of the segment.

The STFT of a signal $x(t)$ is defined as:

$$X(t, f) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(\tau) \cdot w(\tau - t) \cdot e^{-j2\pi f\tau} d\tau \quad (1)$$

Where:

- $x(t)$: current signal in time domain
- $w(\tau-t)$: window function that is applied to the signal to localize it in time
- $e^{-j2\pi f\tau}$: complex exponential used to extract the frequency components
- t : time
- f : frequency

The window function ensures that the signal is localized within a small-time frame for each analysis. It slides across the signal, and for each position t , a Fourier transform is computed on the windowed portion of the signal. The resulting spectrogram is a matrix where the horizontal and vertical axes represent time and frequency, respectively. The colour or intensity of the matrix represents the magnitude of the frequency component at a given time, often using a logarithmic scale to enhance visibility of weaker frequencies.

3. IMPLEMENTATION OF SPECTROGRAM IN PYTHON PLATFORM

Once the 3-phase current signal data was successfully collected under all experimental conditions, the time-series data for each phase was transformed into 2-dimensional (2-D) images using the spectrogram conversion technique. This entire conversion process was executed within the Python environment. The subsequent section provides a detailed discussion on the libraries used, the spectrogram conversion process, and the development of the Graphical User Interface (GUI).

3.1 Useful libraries of the Python Environment

The names and applications of the library files which were installed in Python, for the current scope of study have been listed in Table 2.

Table 2. List of imported libraries in Python

Libraries	Application
tkinter	Used for developing the GUI
openpyxl	Used for importing Excel File and managing the data
matplotlib.pyplot	Used for plotting the output Spectrogram
numpy	Used for performing various mathematical and Scientific operations

3.2 Spectrogram Conversion Using Python

Once the libraries were imported, the next step was to convert the 1-D time-series signals into 2-D spectrogram images. The following steps were then performed to accomplish this transformation process-

- Data importing: Initially, the collected data in .csv format was converted to .xlsx format. The converted data was then imported into the .py file, where it was subsequently stored in an array.

- Extraction of single cycle current data: Throughout the experiment, multiple cycles of current data were recorded for each observation. However, for the purpose of further analysis, only a complete cycle, consisting of both the positive and negative halves of the current signals, was considered. As a result, the current data for each phase was stored as a single cycle in a separate array.

- Image conversion: Spectrogram conversion was applied to the array containing the single-cycle current data for each phase. The resulting spectrogram was then displayed in the plots section of the IDE and simultaneously saved to the specified folder.

3.3 Development of Graphical User Interface (GUI)

A user-friendly GUI was developed to make the spectrogram conversion process more user-friendly and efficient. Key features of the GUI include the following:

- Open File Selection: Users can select files or directories containing the collected data for processing;
- Setting the parameters: Users have the flexibility to specify the desired “NFFT” and “overlap value” for the spectrogram output, allowing for the customization of the dataset;
- Output Management: Users can store spectrogram images to user-specified locations.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After collecting the current data, each set of current signals was normalized by referencing the peak value of the corresponding phase currents recorded under the healthy no-load condition. This normalization process eliminates the influence of amplitude variations caused by load fluctuations or other external factors, ensuring more accurate fault detection. Figures 3(a) and 3(b) illustrate the 3-phase normalized current waveforms captured under the H_NL and IR_NL conditions, respectively.

Figure 3. 3-phase current signals obtained at (a) healthy no-load and (b) IR fault no-load conditions

Upon conducting a preliminary visual check of the current waveforms, no significant differences were apparent when the operating conditions were varied. Therefore, the time-series data for each phase current signal were converted into 2-D images through spectrogram analysis. Figure 4 to 7 present the spectrogram images of the 3-phase current signals under both healthy and IR fault conditions at no-load and load conditions, respectively.

Figure 4. Spectrogram image of 3-phase currents at healthy and no-load condition [NFFT = 8, Overlap = 6]

Figure 5. Spectrogram image of 3-phase currents at IR fault and no-load condition [NFFT = 8, Overlap = 6]

Figure 6. Spectrogram image of 3-phase currents at healthy and loaded condition [NFFT = 8, Overlap = 6]

Figure 7. Spectrogram image of 3-phase currents at IR fault and loaded condition [NFFT = 8, Overlap = 6]

From Figure 4 to Figure 7 the difference in the power amplitude due to change in operating cases could be observed in the frequency band of 4000 Hz to 6000 Hz. Comparison of exemplary spectrogram parameters i.e. time & power amplitude on 5000 Hz frequency obtained from 3-phase currents under motor no-load and loaded conditions are listed in Table 3 and Table 4, respectively.

Table 3. Power Amplitude in No-Load Condition

R-Phase			Y-Phase			B-Phase		
Time	Healthy	Fault	Time	Healthy	Fault	Time	Healthy	Fault
0.0051	-85.4683	-86.9205	0.0082	-90.3369	-91.6082	0.0115	-89.8747	-91.0695
0.0052	-82.2565	-87.8916	0.0083	-84.9414	-93.7239	0.0116	-84.8426	-95.6029
0.0053	-80.3245	-86.0616	0.0084	-82.0686	-95.4648	0.0117	-80.991	-97.0416
0.0054	-78.2094	-91.3081	0.0085	-80.8702	-89.7949	0.0118	-78.4135	-94.3067
0.0055	-77.3236	-88.5315	0.0086	-77.9032	-88.0933	0.0119	-76.7021	-94.4407
0.0056	-76.1091	-97.1189	0.0087	-76.8779	-92.5925	0.012	-74.5998	-96.2951
0.0057	-74.96	-91.9691	0.0088	-74.8239	-93.647	0.0121	-73.6081	-89.2331
0.0058	-74.4134	-95.8146	0.0089	-74.2235	-94.4428			
0.0059	-73.7489	-94.2941						

Table 4. Power Amplitude in Load Condition

R-Phase			Y-Phase			B-Phase		
Time	Healthy	Fault	Time	Healthy	Fault	Time	Healthy	Fault
0.0051	-75.9629	-94.2126	0.0082	-85.93	-94.9842	0.0115	-90.3638	-91.6721
0.0052	-74.7916	-90.6704	0.0083	-79.0113	-90.5215	0.0116	-92.297	-98.0408
0.0053	-74.8206	-92.2962	0.0084	-79.0256	-99.7528	0.0117	-91.9337	-93.3356

0.0054	-75.1245	-89.2259	0.0085	-76.4095	-89.5918	0.0118	-87.7999	-98.0924
0.0055	-76.5114	-92.4631	0.0086	-77.645	-92.688	0.0119	-85.1585	-98.4426
0.0056	-79.167	-91.8105	0.0087	-78.1611	-87.4699	0.012	-88.2472	-95.4848
0.0057	-80.3898	-94.9701	0.0088	-80.2112	-88.8041	0.0121	-86.2251	-94.726
0.0058	-85.9898	-93.991	0.0089	-82.5909	-87.4246			
0.0059	-84.2379	-93.2291						

In the range of time listed in Table 3 and Table 4, the power amplitude corresponding to fault cases on the both no load and load conditions are significantly higher compared to the values at healthy condition. Therefore, these power amplitudes may be considered as significant features for faults classification.

It may further be noted that, the GUI facilitates seamless data conversion, and the spectrograms effectively highlight the differences between ideal and faulty conditions. By visually comparing the spectrograms, their utility in assessing motor health becomes apparent. The findings also suggest that further development of automated algorithms could enhance fault detection by utilizing spectrogram features.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This research proves effective results of spectrogram analysis in processing the stator current signals of 3 phase induction motors. A strong foundation for determining the health of a motor is established by the primary emphasis on data collecting, format conversion, signal translation, and GUI development. The present study can be extended to investigate more frequency components of spectrogram images for detailed frequency analysis. Moreover, the spectrogram characteristics may be used to automate fault classification through the integration of machine learning and deep learning models.

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